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The Blended Librarian, Redefining Librarianship

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THE BLENDED LIBRARIAN, REDEFINING LIBRARIANSHIP

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ABSTRACT

The Planet Earth and its components are always in a state of dynamics. Similarly, all the professions that exist are also in a state of dynamics. So, how can librarianship be left behind. There has been continuous evolution of libraries as well as librarianship. This paper aims at studying the evolution of librarianship and the changing roles of the librarian.

Keywords: Blended Librarian, EdTech, Skills, Academic Libraries, Sheffield Model.

1. INTRODUCTION

The field of library and information science have always been subjected to an engaging, ever-changing, always in a state of flux trend. The past few decades have seen an upsurge in the development of the technology and the way that it has gotten itself nested in every process of life. The library has evolved from clay tablets to the present world e-books. The role of the librarian has undergone continuous evolution to meet the social and technological needs of the users of the libraries. From just the record keeper of books the librarian has evolved to the librarian, the data scientist, the informationist, the cybrarian and now blended librarian.

In this technology driven world, the user does not need to actually visit a library to get access to information or books. Books and information is available at the touch of a button. To survive and sustain, change is inevitable. As rightly stated by Charles Darwin, It is not the strongest of the species that survive, nor the most intelligent, but the one most responsive to change. In short, it is the survival of the fittest, a phrase derived from the Darwinian

Evolutionary theory. What is meant here is that, the library and information science professionals have to keep themselves always updated with the current events as well as the innovations that take place in technology so as to keep the libraries thriving.

The library infrastructure itself has undergone various changes to meet the needs of the community. The library service have moved from the collection centric model to the user centric model. In accordance, the role of the librarian has also changed from that just the record keeper and issuer of books to that of an academician and an information scientist so as to meet the need of the changing library spaces and places and also the needs of the community.

2. BLENDED LIBRARIAN / LIBRARIANSHIP

The term 'Blended Librarian' or 'Blended Librarianship' first made its emergence in the year 2004. It is a concept developed by Steven Bell, Director of the Paul J. Gutman Library at Philadelphia University and John Shank, Head of Instructional Design Services and Instructional design librarian at Penn State Berks- Lehigh Valley College.

According to Bell and Shank, the blended librarian first combines the traditional aspects of librarianship with the technological skills of an information technologist, ie. The software and hardware related skills (Blended Librarianship, 2018)

Most of the librarians have already proved their prowess in technology. With technology if we blend the academicians skills of curriculum design and instructional skills, what we have is the blended librarian. So, in simple words, a blended librarian is a blend of the traditional librarian, the academician and the technologist. With all this mashup of skills and services, the blended librarian offers the best possible combination for enhanced learning and teaching process.

A blended librarian in other words is someone who has library and information science skills integrated with information and communication technology (ICT) skills i.e. hardware and software skills and instructional design or teaching skills. The blended

librarian needs to apply the right technology in the teaching learning process.

Carrie A. McDonald in the research paper defines Blended librarian as, ‘A Blended Librarian seamlessly combines 21st century skills, instructional research and design, and technological skills into their existing library program. Through these skills, the librarian is able to make more and better connections with faculty, students, and patrons’ (McDonald, 2011).

Figure 1: The Evolving Librarian

(Source: https://cdn-images-1.medium.com/max/1200/1*TG9CSfBvNJ9lwY9eabY1vQ.jpeg)

	Historical	Emerging	Future
Collections	Just-in-case	Just-in-time	On demand, anytime
Space	Static, mostly for collections	Flexible, user-focused	Embedded in academic units, a collaborative space for Knowmads
User Experience	Unintentional	Experimentation with service design	Academic libraries as campus leaders in community engagement
Reference	In person, over the phone	Digital	Highly automated, mobile
Users	Students, faculty at their home institution	MOOCs, New majority learners, unaffiliated global learners	Community members, Knowmads
Skills	Master's of Library Science, subject specialists	Blended Librarians	Entrepreneurial Blended Librarians
Teaching & Learning	Assist students and faculty with research assignments, drop-in sessions by request	Embedded in colleges, departments, and courses	Blended Librarians
Demonstrating Value	Collection size	Expanding partnerships on campus, create evidence for invisible services	Learning analytics
Relationships with Faculty	Limited, based on research needs	Co-creative, joint research projects	Partnerships with unaffiliated research entrepreneurs

Figure 2: The future libraries & librarians

(Source: <https://educationfutures.com/storage/app/uploads/public/5b196f7c8/5b196f7c81fa5991960725.jpg>)

Figure 2 illustrates how the libraries have evolved to the current state and how it will be in the future.

3. UNDERSTANDING THE BLENDED LIBRARIAN / LIBRARIANSHIP

From all the above stated descriptions and definitions it can be safely stated that, a blended librarian is an academician (academic librarian) who now forms the integral part of teaching learning process. Based on Shanks, Bells and McDonalds definition, there are a few pointers that will help us understand the blended librarian.

1. The Academic librarian, who works in co-ordination with the faculty and other stakeholders of an institution are expected to have understanding of some important issues like,
 - Changes in Curriculum issues – in the library field, there have been significant changes in the curriculum with regards to classification, cataloguing, reference work etc. There is a poor coverage in professional education when it comes to LIS. These loopholes and drawbacks need to be addressed by conducting refresher courses and orientations.
 - Research issues –the librarian should take care that the library does not only limit itself to the role of the book store, but activities etc. should be conducted in such a way as to help in the research activities of the institute. Hence, the library itself transforming into a research library. According to the Online Dictionary of Library and Information Science, a research library is the one that contains comprehensive collection of materials in a specific field, academic discipline or group of disciplines which includes primary and secondary sources that are selected to meet the information needs of serious researchers.
 - Issues in University / Institute Ranking – the rank of the institute depends on the points gained by the library. The librarian should keep a lookout to see that his or her library fulfills all the criteria laid down by AICTE or UGC, NAAC, NBA and other governing bodies.

- Accreditation issues – the librarian should take care that the norms like procurement of book titles and volumes, subscription to journals and e packages, and other requirements have been fulfilled as per the rules laid down by governing bodies before accreditations are conducted for the institutions.
- 2. The librarianship skills - the blended librarian has to be proficient in his/her own field. These skills include circulation, reference services, classification and cataloguing, library automation etc.
- 3. Software skills – the librarian should have knowledge of operating system, various library management softwares like NGL, KOHA; writing software such as MS-Word, Powerpoint, excel etc. They should be good with social media usage. They should have knowledge of research related softwares and other softwraes that will help the library and its motives of supporting the institute in its academic and research pursuits.
- 4. Hardware skills – the librarians should have basic knowledge of computer and network related hardware specially related to the library.
- 5. The librarian should have the ability for instructional design which is necessary to analyze the learning needs and goals to meet the needs of the patrons. This would include developing modules and activities on how to access e-journals, referencing, citation etc.
- 6. The librarian should keep himself or herself with the latest technologies and the new digital ways of teaching, the use of different media for preparing presentations, workshops etc., use of Moodle, PowerPoint, smartboards, blogs etc.

4. THE POSTULATES OF BLENDED LIBRARIANSHIP

1. For the critical success of delivery of library services to the present information society, the librarian needs to take up the role of innovator and an agent of change.

2. The librarian should commit him or herself to develop campus wide information literacy drives which in the process would facilitate the ongoing teaching learning processes.
3. The LIS professional should design and develop educational and instructional programs and hold workshops and seminars for the users to help them understand and learn about accessing the library services and other information and training that is required for developing skills etc. that will benefit their future.
4. The librarian needs to develop programs and services in collaboration with instructional technologists. This is a required so as to facilitate the instructional mission of the academic libraries.
5. The librarian need to implement change in library instruction through adaptiveness, creativity, proactiveness and bringing about innovation in the newly developed services.
6. The librarian needs to coordinate and develop a relationship, a partnership with the faculty in a bid to integrate technology and library resources into the instructional courses. This will enhance the student learning and assessment of the outcome in the arena of information access, retrieval and integration.
7. Partner with the staff of information technology section to transform the reference desk to a digital information desk and services.
8. The blended librarian should be available for individual appointments and one to one consultations with his or her patrons rather than just sitting in the library waiting for the patrons to approach them. This can be done by online chatting as in the feature like 'Ask A Librarian.
9. Try to recruit bright and techno savvy bright students and train and mentor them to assist other students in the library.
10. Schedule for group discussions with small groups of faculty

or students to instruct regarding the teaching learning processes embedded with the library services.

11. Develop online tutorials / programs/ guides that will help the patrons learn what they want at their own pace.

5. SHEFFIELD MODEL OF BLENDED INFORMATION PROFESSIONALS

Figure3: Sheffield model of blended information professionals.

(Source: Corral, 2010) (https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Sheffield-model-of-blended-information-professionals_fig2_47870078)

In the above Sheffield model, three broad categories of hybrid or blended professionals can be identified.

The first category is the **E-content and digital library specialists** which is a blend of ‘**content specialists**’ and ‘**conduit specialists**’. The electronic resource co-ordinators, repository librarians, digital collection managers, web managers, intranet managers fall under this category.

The second category is of the **Discipline-based information and knowledge specialists** which is a blend of the ‘**context specialists**’, ‘**content specialists**’ and the ‘**conduit specialists**’. This category includes the subject librarians, instructional design librarians, data librarians, GIS specialists, data scientists.

The third category is that of the **Context-specific technology and media specialists** which is a blend of the ‘**context specialists**’ and ‘**conduit specialists**’. The computer assisted learning specialists, educational technologists, instructional technologists, learning technologists come under this category.

6. BLENDED LIBRARIAN : SKILLS NEEDED

A. TECHNOLOGY SKILLS

1. **PowerPoint:**Microsoft PowerPoint is not just meant for making great presentations. It can be used to develop interactive tutorials without any additional plugins. The librarian needs to be thorough with the knowledge of using PowerPoint.
2. **HTML / Dreamweaver / WordPress:** All what we see on the net, either websites, wikis, blogs or even tube videos require some or the other sort of coding. It is necessary to at least know how to read errors if not write the codes. The librarian can learn the basics of HTML. Now we get desktop tools like Dreamweaver which is a tool for designing a website and also open source software's like WordPress which already come with HTML. We can use these tools to develop online tutorials, design online library guides etc.
3. **Screen casting:**Screen casting is the new form of e-learning. A screencast may be defined as a digital recording of the computer screen which usually includes audio narrations. Screencasts are one of the many types of instructional videos. Screen casting saves a lot of time that is spent on answering the same questions again and again. Screen casting can be used to develop tutorials, training videos, video lessons, recorded presentations, service demos, feedbacks etc. The advantage of screen casting is that the patron can watch the screencasts at a time best suited for him or her and also absorb the information at their own pace. Screen casts add a personal touch compared to the other methods. The librarian can get the screen casting software installed like Camtasia.
4. **Learning Analytics:**Learning Analytics is the process of collecting, measuring, analyzing and reporting data about learners, the learning experiences and learning programs. The academic libraries have over the decades

evaluated their collections and services with qualitative and quantitative methods. The librarian needs to update oneself with the skills pertaining to learning analytics to improve the success of the patrons with implications for the library.

1. **Cloud Computing:** Cloud Computing or cloud-based learning is being used in every field today. It is the next generation form of e-learning. Cloud computing allows access to hardware and software through internet. Cloud computing simplifies processes and saves time by helping in avoiding hosting of multiple servers and equipment's locally and constantly dealing with hardware failures, installation of software's, and the upgrades and compatibility issues of the software's. The LIS professionals should make use of this technology. The blended librarians need to update him/herself with the latest cloud-based applications such as Evernote, DropBox, Google Docs, Zotero and many more.

B. MORE SKILLS

1. **Teaching Skills:** A blended librarian is a teacher, an educator. But most of the librarians find it difficult to instruct or conduct workshops for their patrons due to lack of teaching skills. The patrons normally find the workshops conducted by the librarians to be very boring. To make the workshops or orientations and other library programs fun filled and engaging the librarians need to enroll one self in a basic course in instructional technology and design to gain some formal or informal knowledge about teaching.
2. The librarian needs to be aggressive to take up leadership opportunities, speak the language of the non LIS professional.
3. **Engage the patrons with EdTech:** EdTech is the short form for educational technology. It refers to making use of technology in the teaching learning process for better outcomes. The librarian needs to keep exploring the new technologies available.

- Convert the libraries into activity hubs by encouraging collaborative activities like video making, creation of digital music, etc.
- Enlighten the students on using EdTech by developing tutorials or conducting workshops. Make the patrons digitally literate.
- Give the patrons digitized curated content in the form of e-books other than the regular hard bound information sources.
- Train the patrons to search for their needs using EdTech tools rather than the librarian fishing for the information required by the patron.
- Encourage the use of digital readers, kindles, computerized check in check outs etc.
- Increase digital collection which saves on space.
- Inter library loaning process sometimes is very time-consuming. To tackle this problem, virtual access to resources can be given from the collaborating libraries which saves the time of the user.
- The LIS professional can develop digital resources and advocate for it among the patrons.
- The LIS professional him/ herself should stay current with EdTech.

CONCLUSION

The librarian has always been perceived as a facilitator, a mediator, an instructor who caters to the information and knowledge needs of the patrons. In the present scenario we can say that some of the skills and roles required have evolved over the years, but certain skills and roles required now are needed to be imbibed and embedded in the LIS field and professionals in a revolutionary manner. The role of the library has changed over a period of years within the library and at the same time the role of the librarian has changed within the library. The changing roles presents the LIS professional with a lot of challenges but at the same time opens a wide arena of possibilities.

If the library and information professionals want the library to be viable and should be able to sustain in this technologically advancing world, then we need to reaffirm the libraries as learning centers for exploring and sharing knowledge and evolving our self as the blended librarian is the cue to making this successful. Our focus should be on the future and not the past.

By embracing 'Blended Librarianship', the library professionals can seamlessly integrate the 21st century skills, technological skills and instructional research and design into their existing library program and in turn develop better connections with the faculty, students and patrons.

The 'Blended Librarian' is a leader, an innovator who embeds the following functions to his or her profile, namely an information unit manager, a mediator of information resources and an educator focused on the development of information literacy of the user community that is served. The 'Blended Librarian' dons various hats, that of the educator, facilitator, mediator, instructional designer, project manager, colleague, learner etc.

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